

GRAMMATICAL CATEGORY OF MOOD IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: In this thesis the issues of comparing verb moods in English are discussed.

Key words: typology, comparison, verb mood, category.

ГРАММАТИЧЕСКАЯ КАТЕГОРИЯ ГЛАГОЛА В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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Аннотация: В данной дипломной работе рассматриваются вопросы сравнения наклонение глаголов в английском языке.

Ключевые слова: типология, сравнение, наклонение глагола, категория.

INGLIZ TILIDA FE'L MAYLI GRAMMATIK KATEGORIASI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisdagi ingliz tilida fe'l mayllarini qiyoslash masalalari muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: tipologiya, qiyoslash, fe'l mayli, kategoriya

The meaning of this category is the attitude of the speaker or writer towards the content of the sentence, whether the speaker considers the action real, unreal, desirable, necessary, etc. It is expressed in the form of the verb.

There are three moods in English - the indicative mood, the imperative mood and the oblique mood. The indicative mood form shows that what is said must be regarded as a fact, as something which has occurred or is occurring at the moment of speaking or will occur in the future. It may denote actions with different time-reference and different aspective characteristics. Therefore the indicative mood has a wide variety of tense and aspect forms in the active and passive voice.

The imperative mood expresses a command or a request to perform an action addressed to somebody, but not the action itself. As it does not actually denote an action as a real act, it has no tense category. The unfulfilled action always refers to the future. Aspect distinctions and voice distinctions are not characteristic of the imperative mood, although forms such as, be writing, be warned sometimes occur. This form is always addressed to the second person. The oblique mood expresses non-facts: unreal or hypothetical actions or states. A hypothetical action or state may be viewed upon as desired, necessary, possible, supposed, imaginary, or contradicting reality.

Availability question iconic relationship Uzbek and English language typology of grammatical category of mood contributed to the accumulation of a large amount of information on this problem, Arakin" "Сравнительная типология ", M.I.Rasulova, Z.I.Shukurova, American linguists J. Greenburg, Ch. Ostgood and J. Genkings, William Croft.

In order to accomplish the proposed aim, objectives and tasks of this theoretical and practical work we can use observation, description, data analysis and processing and the questionnaire methods.

Used literature:

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